

ON MODE I FATIGUE TESTING OF ALUMINIUM/EPOXY ADHESIVE BONDS

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ABSTRACT

The mode I fatigue crack growth rate in aluminium/rubber modified epoxy bonds is studied as a function of applied stress intensity factor range and bond thickness. Crack growth is tracked by means of a specially developed electronic grid monitoring system. The Paris power law is used to characterise the test data and has been modified accordingly to model the mode I fatigue crack growth behaviour over all bond thicknesses. The fatigue crack path has been studied and shown to depend upon bond thickness, whilst fatigue crack growth is generally less stable at smaller bond thicknesses.

Keywords: Adhesive bonds, fatigue, rubber toughened epoxy, Paris law.

1. INTRODUCTION

In the air defence industry, the importance of adhesive bonds in the development of advanced aircraft is well known. However, they are of equal importance in relation to repairs of existing aircraft, as a repair is only as effective as the adhesive used. Therefore, the micromechanisms of failure within the bond and its effective life span, especially in fatigue, are essential knowledge if expensive and potentially disastrous mistakes are to be avoided.

Fatigue crack growth is a phenomenon of damage and separation of material ahead of a crack under cyclic loading. The cause of fatigue damage accumulation is cyclic plastic straining, and so the fatigue damage of material elements ahead of the crack tip due to cyclic fatigue occurs only within the reversed plastic zone which is embedded inside the monotonic plastic zone [1]. When a material element is enveloped by the reverse plastic zone and the plastic strain exceeds a threshold value, it begins to experience fatigue damage and as soon as its ductility is exhausted, the material element will fail.

The fracture mechanics of aluminium/epoxy adhesive bonds are reasonably well documented [2,3]. However, the effect of fatigue loading on such geometries is a fairly recent initiative, and the effect of such parameters as bond thickness on the fatigue crack growth rate is not known. Both double cantilever beam (DCB) [4,5] and compact tension (CT) [6,7] test geometries are documented, although the DCB geometry now seems to be used mostly for composite/epoxy and metal/rubber bonds. Also, it is limited as to its accuracy over a large range of crack propagation rates [7].

Rubber modified epoxy (RME) is preferred as an adhesive bond material because of its enhanced crack growth resistance when compared to standard epoxy adhesives. Fatigue of RME can take place in two forms; high cycle fatigue and low cycle fatigue, the difference being that low cycle fatigue is defined as cyclic fatigue within the plastic region of the material. Also, the surface extension of microcracks is predominant, whereas their bulk propagation is dominating in high cycle fatigue. Studies on the low cycle fatigue failure micromechanisms are uncommon [8-12] and have for the most part been inconclusive. Analysis of hysteresis loops [8] has revealed that cyclic softening of the material is a major damage mechanism. Failure occurred by microcracking of the matrix, followed by bridging of these microcracks by the rubber particles resulting in a toughening effect, and final fracture occurs when the microcracks coalesce into macrocracks by particle/matrix debonding. The degree of matrix damage was found to be dependent on parameters such as cyclic strain range and test frequency, although these observations were only tentative. Several other microscopic deformation modes have been identified such as shear yielding, crystallisation resulting from shear banding, crazing and molecular reorientation.

Mode I cyclic fatigue of aluminium/epoxy bonds has attracted little interest and so understanding of the damage processes that occur is very limited. Firstly, the effect of bond thickness needs to be established, as small bond sizes will constrict the formation of the plastic zone, possibly resulting in a different failure mode. Secondly, steady state crack propagation rates may change according to the bond thickness and may also be dependant on the fracture path taken i.e. through the resin or along the resin/aluminium interface in which case, adherend surface preparation is a factor.

The work reported in this paper details the effect on the mode I fatigue crack propagation rate of applied stress intensity factor and bond thickness, and reports on the difficulties encountered with the test setup and their suggested remedies.

2. EXPERIMENTAL DETAILS

2.1. Test material

The rubber modified epoxy test material consisted of CIBA GEIGY GY260 epoxy resin hardened with piperidine and contained 15 wt% of Hycar 1300X13 CTBN liquid rubber. The constituents were blended and degassed and cured at 120°C for 16 hours at atmospheric pressure.

2.2. Test geometry

The test specimens were of the compact tension type, as schematically shown in figure 1. This geometry was chosen due to extensive in-house experience [6] and because this geometry is easily adapted for use with the electronic data acquisition unit developed for fatigue crack monitoring. The adherends were 6061 aluminium alloy blocks, 85mm long, 20mm wide and 8mm thick and were bonded together in a specially designed fixture that allowed the manufacture of specimens of various bond thicknesses whilst preserving the original adherend dimensions. The specimens were precracked during manufacture by the insertion of a thin Teflon sheet between the adherends at one end. The aluminium surfaces were surface treated according to the ASTM specification [13].

Figure 1 Typical CT test specimen used for mode I fatigue testing showing a crack of length a in the mid-plane of the specimen of bond thickness b (all dimensions in mm). The fixture holes are 6mm in diameter.

2.3. Test procedures

An Instron servohydraulic testing facility was used to perform all tests, with the test piece supported by specially designed fork grips. All tests were performed under constant load control, with ΔK increasing with increasing crack length. Crack growth was monitored by screen printing a specially designed grid consisting of a series of thin equidistant lines, 1mm apart, onto the specimen surface using a silk screen mesh and electrically conducting black ink. Prior to grid application, the aluminium had to be coated in an insulating layer. This layer had to be of a material that would crack only when breached by the crack front, otherwise erroneous data would result. Several coatings were investigated and the coating system deemed to give the most reliable results consisted of a household primer coating followed by a thin layer of car aerosol paint.

The data collection system functioned on the principle that the resistance of the grid changed each time a grid line was broken i.e. the electrical resistance of the system was simply related to the fatigue crack length. Such a system has been previously used [14] to accurately monitor fatigue crack growth rates in single edge notch specimens made from polyvinyl chloride, high impact polystyrene and acrylonitrile butadiene-styrene. The grid was connected to the data acquisition unit by means of specially fabricated 32-way electrical sockets clipped to the specimen. The experimental setup is shown in figure 2, and clearly shows the morphology of the grid, and the propagated fatigue crack.

All mode I fatigue tests were performed at a frequency of 1Hz, a load ratio of 0.1 and at ambient temperature (25°C). Specimens of three different bond thicknesses were tested (0.6mm, 0.8mm and 2.1mm) and for comparative purposes, bulk resin specimens of identical dimensions to the bond adherends were also tested.

For an applied load ratio, the applied ΔK needs to be obtained for data reduction purposes. In the bonded joint, the relationship between load, P , and applied stress intensity factor, K , has been established by Mai and Vipond [6] in terms of crack length, a , specimen width, W , specimen thickness, B , and the moduli of the aluminium adherends (E_{al}) and the rubber modified epoxy (E_{ep}) i.e.

$$K = \frac{P}{B\sqrt{W}} \sqrt{\left(\frac{E_{op}}{E_{a1}}\right)} \left[29.6 \left(\frac{a}{W}\right)^{\frac{1}{2}} - 185.5 \left(\frac{a}{W}\right)^{\frac{3}{2}} + 655.7 \left(\frac{a}{W}\right)^{\frac{5}{2}} - 1017 \left(\frac{a}{W}\right)^{\frac{7}{2}} + 638.9 \left(\frac{a}{W}\right)^{\frac{9}{2}} \right] \quad (1)$$

For the bulk resin CT specimens, this relationship is according to equation 2 [15]:

$$K = \frac{P}{B\sqrt{W}} \left[\frac{2 + \frac{a}{W}}{\left(1 - \frac{a}{W}\right)^{\frac{3}{2}}} \left(0.886 + 4.64 \frac{a}{W} - 13.32 \left(\frac{a}{W}\right)^2 + 14.72 \left(\frac{a}{W}\right)^3 - 5.6 \left(\frac{a}{W}\right)^4 \right) \right] \quad (2)$$

The definitive description of fatigue crack growth rates in terms of applied stress intensity factor is given by the Paris power law [16]:

$$\frac{da}{dN} = \alpha (\Delta K)^\beta \quad (3)$$

where α and β are characterising constants dependent on factors such as load ratio, temperature and frequency. The tests performed aimed to establish the dependence of α and β on the thickness of the adhesive bond.

Figure 2 An *in situ* mode I fatigue test showing the electronic crack monitoring system and the propagated fatigue crack.

3. RESULTS

The results presented in figure 3 show the logarithmic variation of da/dN with ΔK and bond thickness. The values for the Paris constants α and β are reported in table 1.

Figure 3 The variation of fatigue crack growth rate (da/dN) with applied ΔK for bond thicknesses of 0.6mm, 0.8mm, 2.1mm and for bulk resin specimens.

Several observations may be made relating to figure 3. Firstly, increasing the bond thickness decreased the value of β and increased the value of α . As β defines the rate of change of crack growth rate with applied ΔK , crack growth appears at its most sensitive to stress variations at the smaller bond thicknesses. The bulk resin data shows that the value of β for the 2.1mm bond thickness is a minimum value.

BOND THICKNESS (mm)	$\ln\alpha$	β
0.6	-45.0	21.74
0.8	-34.1	12.82
2.1	-22.6	7.00
bulk resin (∞)	-28.4	6.95

Table 1 The constants α and β used in the Paris power law

Secondly, the observed value of ΔK_{max} , the maximum stress intensity range above which crack growth was rapid and unstable, decreased with decreasing bond thickness. K is related to the plastic zone size, w , ahead of the crack front [17] according to equation 4.

$$w = \frac{\pi}{8} \left(\frac{K}{\sigma_y} \right)^2 \tag{4}$$

where σ_y is the yield strength of the resin. From previous work [8], σ_y is approximately 90MPa and the bulk resin fatigue data are within 10% of those reported in other sources [18]. From equation 4, the plastic zone size in the bulk material is approximately 0.03mm, therefore implying that bond thicknesses greater than 0.03mm should not be constrained by the aluminium adherends and possess values of β approaching the bulk resin value. This is clearly not so. There are two possible explanations; firstly the presence of the adherends restricts the development of the full plastic region, thus rendering equation 4 inapplicable. Secondly, the value of σ_y is inappropriate, as crack growth occurs preferentially at the aluminium/ adhesive interface, and not in the bulk resin. It is unlikely that the yield strengths of the adhesive and the interface are identical.

Thirdly, experimental scatter increased with decreasing bond thickness. This may have been caused by fatigue crack propagation becoming irregular below a certain bond thickness due to processing irregularities. Another cause may be the crack path varying from one aluminium/epoxy interface to the other. The fracture morphology schematically illustrated in figure 4 was typical for bond thicknesses below 0.8mm. As the specimens were not annealed prior to testing, residual stresses could also effect the crack growth data.

Fourthly, the value of β for the 0.6mm bond thickness is rather high. This may be due to the fatigue crack propagating through the aluminium/epoxy interface, rather than through a bulk material. No comparative data were available and so a value of 21.74 for crack propagation through an interface may be reasonable.

Figure 4 Showing a typical mode I fatigue failure morphology obtained from a specimen of bond thickness 0.6mm showing intermittent fracture across the adhesive.

The fatigue crack path in specimens of bond thickness 2.1mm never deviated between the aluminium/epoxy interfaces, thus resulting in a uniform fracture morphology and regular crack growth.

From table 1, the Paris power law may be normalised to account for the effects of bond thickness (b), and thus provide a degree of predictive modelling for the fatigue behaviour of bonded aluminium joints. If the bulk resin specimens are regarded as adhesive joints of infinite bond thickness, then:

$$\frac{da}{dN} = \beta \Delta K^\alpha \tag{5}$$

where $\check{\alpha}$ and \check{c} are functions of bond thickness, given by

$$\check{\alpha} = -28.4 + \frac{1}{b^3}(26.82b^2 - 34.21b + 7.23) \tag{6}$$

and

$$\check{c} = 6.903 + \frac{1}{b^3}(-0.67b^2 - 3.63 \times 10^{-3}b + 3.44) \tag{7}$$

The model can be used to normalise the test data as shown in figure 5. This figure was constructed by normalising the da/dN values and plotting $\ln[1/\check{\alpha}(da/dN)]/\check{c}$ versus $\ln\Delta K$. Figure 5 shows that the Paris power law constants can therefore be predicted for bond thicknesses in the range $0.6\text{mm} \leq b \leq \infty$.

Figure 5 Normalised fatigue crack growth rate as a function of applied ΔK for bond thicknesses of 0.6mm, 0.8mm, 2.1mm and for bulk resin specimens.

The testing program highlighted several difficulties with the test specimen. Testing under constant load resulted in the fatigue crack only propagating through half of the grid lines before the onset of unstable growth. Halting the test before unstable growth occurred and reducing the applied load resulted in extended specimen life. Several sets of test data had to be discarded, as their insulating coating was not cracking with the crack front. If the coating was too thick, then the plastic deformation at the crack tip was not sufficient to breach the coating. Quality control for the insulating layer was difficult to achieve, and this phenomenon was only detected during the data reduction.

4. CONCLUSIONS

An electric data acquisition unit has been developed and successfully used to monitor mode I fatigue crack growth rates in aluminium/epoxy adhesive joints of varying bond thickness. Minor problems occurred relating to the thickness of the insulating coating, and improvements to this coating will be investigated.

Fatigue crack growth rates exhibit a greater dependence on applied stress intensity range at smaller bond thicknesses, and the Paris power law constants have been determined for various bond thicknesses.

A modified Paris power law has been developed that accounts for the effect of bond thickness on the fatigue crack growth rate and accurately predicts the Paris power law constants for bond thicknesses in the range $0.6\text{mm} \leq b \leq \infty$.

The fracture morphology of the adhesive bond is different at smaller bond thicknesses than at larger bond thicknesses, with traversing of the adhesive layer to opposite aluminium/adhesive interfaces more common at these smaller thicknesses.

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